

components were observed for pathways and crosses \times pathways interactions, suggesting that environment had a minimal effect on the comparative yielding ability of the two crosses.

Because only two crosses were studied, these results are not conclusive. But it appears probable that there are no advantages in early generation selection under dryland conditions. Consid-

ering the many operational advantages, dryland rice breeders should consider growing all early generation materials under wetland conditions. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Identification of iron toxicity in Brazil

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Symptoms similar to those of iron toxicity have been observed in rice-producing regions of Santa Catarina State, Brazil. In 1977, their cause was studied for the first time.

Many brownish spots appeared on the tips of older leaves of affected plants

and later spread to the basal parts. The leaves (except the midrib) turned brown and dried. In many areas the brown color turned reddish. The roots were dark brown and were damaged. All the symptoms were observed at the maximum tillering stage.

At the panicle initiation stage and at maturity, samples of roots, culms, and leaves were collected from a rice farmer's field at Camboriú, Itajaí River Valley. Simultaneously plant samples were collected from another plot where

no symptoms were observed. The samples were sent to different laboratories for analysis of the contents of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, iron, and manganese. One laboratory replicated the sample analysis twice.

The results were compared with those found for various elements by Tanaka and Yoshida in 1970. The iron content of the affected leaves at maturity averaged 846 ppm. Iron toxicity was confirmed as the cause of the symptoms. ■

A mass-screening method for salt tolerance of rice varieties at seedling stage

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Rice varieties at the seedling stage were screened for salt tolerance in the greenhouse at RRS in Chinsurah.

The experiment was designed to investigate the effects of salinity on seedling growth (up to 21 days) of 100 rice varieties — including the standard variety SR26 B — under 17.5 mmho/cm of saline water (see figure). The salt solution was prepared by adding sodium chloride to distilled water. Normal and saline water were maintained at a suitable level in sterilized cylindrical, glass jars (9.5 cm \times 5.0 cm). Salt solution was estimated by determining electrical conductivity in mmho/cm at 25° C of the solution.

Blotting paper rolls were inserted in the glass jars. Two sets of jars, one for each treatment (normal and saline water), were placed side by side. Five seeds of each variety were made to adhere to the blotting paper by means of their seed hairs so the embryos

Germination and seedling growth of the same variety in saline water (left) and fresh water (right).

remained submerged.

Each variety was allowed to germinate in the culture jars. Water, i.e. fresh and saline, was added to the jars and maintained to a depth of 7.0 cm. The salt solution was adjusted to the desired

concentration at weekly intervals. The salt tolerance of each variety at seedling stage was determined by length, fresh weight, dry weight, and water content of root and shoot.

A high concentration of saline water delayed germination and depressed seedling growth for all varieties. General effects of salinity were darkening of the green color, withering of leaf tips, followed by yellowing and drying. A high degree of salinity significantly reduced the length of the root and shoot of the rice seedlings. Root growth was more depressed than was shoot growth.

Marked varietal differences in salt tolerance were observed (see table). Hamilton (selected from Nonabokra), a newly recommended variety, showed the best root growth. Root length development in BPI 76 was poor. Hamilton and Dholabokra had significantly higher values for shoot length than the other varieties. The adverse effect of salinity on shoot length was most pronounced in BPI 76.

Fresh weight and dry matter production of root and shoot also were depressed by salinity. Hamilton gave higher values for fresh weight and water content of root and shoot. But Dheral and Marichsail proved better in shoot

Outstanding rices selected from 100 varieties tested for tolerance for high level of salt (17.5 mmho/cm at 25°C) at the seedling stage. RRS, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Treatment ^a	Root				Shoot			
		Length (cm)	Fresh wt (mg)	Dry wt (mg)	Water content (mg)	Length (cm)	Fresh wt (mg)	Dry wt (mg)	Water content (mg)
Patnai 23	N	16.6	215.0	19.0	196.0	14.4	172.5	27.0	145.5
	S	7.7	85.0	8.5	76.5	4.3	100.0	14.0	86.0
Dheral	N	23.6	103.7	28.3	75.5	25.7	211.3	64.3	147.0
	S	9.0	41.3	13.5	27.7	8.4	129.2	48.0	71.2
TN(I)	N	13.9	212.5	26.3	186.2	9.5	110.0	32.3	78.0
	S	2.2	6.5	3.0	33.4	0.6	12.5	4.3	7.2
IR8	N	15.5	231.7	27.5	203.2	12.5	166.6	40.5	125.1
	S	5.3	42.7	9.3	33.4	1.8	69.2	12.3	46.9
BPI76	N	14.4	135.0	18.5	116.5	7.8	102.5	23.5	79.0
	S	1.6	7.5	2.5	5.0	6.0	11.0	3.5	7.5
Marichsail	N	13.0	147.5	24.3	123.2	17.5	252.5	59.7	192.8
	S	6.7	41.5	12.0	29.5	6.5	121.7	41.0	80.7
Getu	N	15.6	172.5	21.5	151.0	11.9	135.0	23.5	111.5
	S	15.1	95.5	11.0	84.5	8.0	92.5	15.0	77.5
Damoder	N	16.4	93.0	22.0	71.0	16.5	167.5	31.0	136.5
	S	8.3	47.5	12.0	35.3	7.1	90.0	20.0	70.0
Dasal	N	17.8	165.0	30.0	135.0	15.6	160.0	29.0	131.0
	S	7.3	67.5	14.5	53.0	7.1	147.5	18.0	129.0
Dholabokra	N	21.6	217.5	26.5	191.0	22.4	252.5	48.5	204.0
	S	5.6	108.5	15.5	93.0	18.8	145.0	37.0	108.0
Hamilton	N	25.2	220.0	24.0	196.0	22.5	405.0	46.0	359.0
	S	15.9	197.5	13.0	184.5	13.7	215.0	37.5	177.5
SR 26 B	N	15.5	216.5	19.5	197.0	19.1	222.5	47.5	175.0
	S	6.5	100.0	10.0	90.0	6.6	135.0	20.0	115.0

^a N = normal water, S = saline water.

dry weight, closely followed by Hamilton and Dholabokra. Dholabokra had the maximum value for root dry weight.

Among the high yielding varieties, IR8 performed best. TN1 gave minimum values for most of the characteristics.

Hamilton was highly salt tolerant and BPI 76 was the least. Hamilton performed best on most of the characteristics. Because salinity appears to affect the rice plant most adversely at the seedling stage, this greenhouse technique can be profitably used to select salt-tolerant varieties. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Genetic control of submergence tolerance in rice

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The inheritance of submergence tolerance in rice was studied by analyzing the segregation pattern and estimating the genetic parameters of crosses involving the cultivars FR 13A, Kurkaruppan,

Thavalu, Gods Heenati, IR36, and B2433b-Kn-10-1-1-1.

Tests for submergence tolerance were conducted under artificial conditions by submerging 10-day-old seedlings for 7 days in 30-cm water. Water temperature was kept constant at 30°C, and light intensity was maintained at 400 lux at the tray level.

Segregation analyses indicated that at least three dominant genes were involved in the control of tolerance for submergence. Two had duplicate gene

action, and the third was complementary to either of the first two.

Estimation of the genetic parameters showed that additive and nonadditive gene effects were important in the inheritance of submergence tolerance. Dominance and nonallelic interactions were present in all crosses analyzed, and the nonallelic interactions were mostly of the duplicate type.

Estimates of broad sense heritability were low to moderate, indicating that a large portion of the phenotypic variance was due to nongenetic effects. ■

Response of traditional deepwater rice to nitrogen application

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Fertilization is a rare practice in most traditional, deepwater rice fields. Reports indicate positive nitrogen (N) response by some improved, deepwater rice lines in terms of grain yield. But such a response under variable water depths, especially in terms of uptake and utilization, is not well known.

IRRI greenhouse and field experiments indicate that high basal N in deepwater rice produces increased plant length and number of basal tillers. Those attributes are desirable in areas prone to early flooding where rapid elongation of the culm above water level is used to combat flood damage.

High basal tillers are retained in subsequent growth stages under both shallow (25-cm) and medium-deep (75-cm) water levels in a nonelongating type, such as IR42; and in deep (130-cm) water level in an elongating type such as Kalar Harsall. The high survival rate of basal tillers ultimately results in increased grain yields due to a higher number of panicles and spikelets per panicle (Table 1). High basal N also stimulates early nodal rooting and nodal tillering — which contributes to grain yields directly or indirectly by absorption of nutrients from floodwater — and additional panicles. This has been substantiated by production of additional nodal tillers and higher grain yields from topdressing with 40 ppm N